

Synthesis, Magnetic and Spectral Studies of Lanthanide(III) Chloride Complexes of Hydrazones of Isonicotinic Acid Hydrazide

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The hydrazones derived from isonicotinic acid hydrazide are known to possess various biological and chemical properties with many important applications¹. From this laboratory, we have reported several *4f* and *5f*-metal complexes of hydrazones of isonicotinic acid hydrazide^{2,3}. In the present communication, we report the synthesis, magnetic and spectral properties of trivalent lanthanide chlorides with *N*-isonicotinamidobenzalaldimine (INH-BENZ) (1), *N*-isonicotinamidoanisalaldimine (INH-ANSL) (2) and *N*-isonicotinamido-*p*-dimethylaminobenzalaldimine (INH-PDAB) (3).

1:R=H 2:R= *p*-OCH₃ 3: R=*p*-N(CH₃)₂

Results and Discussion

The interaction of LnCl₃ with INH-BENZ, INH-ANSL and INH-PDAB in non-aqueous medium results in the formation of LnCl₃.2L (Table 1). The complexes are anhydrous, quite stable and soluble in common organic solvents. The molar conductance values (1.9–4.3 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) of these complexes determined in PhNO₂ (concn. 10⁻³ M) at ~ 35° suggest their non-electrolytic nature. The molecular weight determinations in freezing PhNO₂ showed them to be monomers. The magnetic moment values are given in Table 1. Except lanthanum(III) complexes, all other complexes are paramagnetic. The magnetic moment values of these complexes show little deviation from Van-Vleck values, indicating that the *4f* electrons do not participate in bond formation⁴.

Infrared spectra : The ligands INH-BENZ, INH-ANSL and INH-PDAB are expected to act as tridentate ligands, the possible coordination sites being pyridinic-nitrogen, azomethine-nitrogen and amide group. Generally, all amides show two absorption bands at ~ 1 640 (C=O) known as amide-I band and 1 600–1 500 cm⁻¹ known as amide-II band. The amide-I band in INH derivatives appear² at 1 660–1 640 cm⁻¹. The complexes show a considerable negative shift in ν_{C=O}, indicating coordination through the carbonyl oxygen atom of the free base. In INH derivatives,

the band at 1 565–1 560 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to amide-II. The ν_{NH} band of the ligands (~ 3 290 and 3 220 cm⁻¹) remains unaffected after complexation. This precludes the possibility of coordination through imine nitrogen. Another ligand band at 1 590 cm⁻¹ (C=N) shifted to lower

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found / (Calcd.)			μ _{eff} B.M.
	Ln	N	Cl	
LaCl ₃ .2(INH-BENZ)	19.85 (19.98)	11.96 12.07	15.17 15.31	Diamag.
PrCl ₃ .2(INH-BENZ)	20.08 (20.21)	11.95 12.04	15.14 15.26	3.69
NdCl ₃ .2(INH-BENZ)	20.42 (20.55)	11.93 11.99	15.07 15.20	3.57
SmCl ₃ .2(INH-BENZ)	21.08 (21.23)	11.80 11.88	14.92 15.07	1.67
GdCl ₃ .2(INH-BENZ)	21.89 (22.00)	11.69 11.77	14.74 14.92	7.93
TbCl ₃ .2(INH-BENZ)	22.11 (22.22)	11.65 11.74	14.71 14.88	9.31
DyCl ₃ .2(INH-BENZ)	22.46 (22.58)	11.59 11.68	14.67 14.81	10.54
LaCl ₃ .2(INH-ANSL)	18.29 (18.39)	11.03 11.11	13.82 14.09	Diamag.
PrCl ₃ .2(INH-ANSL)	18.52 (18.61)	10.99 11.08	13.77 14.05	3.51
NdCl ₃ .2(INH-ANSL)	18.82 (18.93)	10.95 11.04	13.73 14.00	3.50
SmCl ₃ .2(INH-ANSL)	19.47 (19.56)	10.87 10.95	13.69 13.89	1.61
GdCl ₃ .2(INH-ANSL)	20.23 (20.29)	10.76 10.85	13.55 13.76	7.82
TbCl ₃ .2(INH-ANSL)	20.41 (20.50)	10.74 10.83	13.53 13.73	9.50
DyCl ₃ .2(INH-ANSL)	20.77 (20.86)	10.68 10.70	13.48 13.67	10.61
LaCl ₃ .2(INH-PDAB)	17.69 (17.78)	14.24 14.33	13.32 13.62	Diamag.
PrCl ₃ .2(INH-PDAB)	17.91 (17.99)	14.19 14.29	13.30 13.59	3.63
NdCl ₃ .2(INH-PDAB)	17.93 (18.03)	14.13 14.24	13.26 13.54	3.53
SmCl ₃ .2(INH-PDAB)	18.80 (18.92)	14.04 14.13	13.21 13.43	1.64
GdCl ₃ .2(INH-PDAB)	19.49 (19.63)	13.90 14.00	13.11 13.32	7.84
TbCl ₃ .2(INH-PDAB)	19.70 (19.83)	13.86 13.97	13.06 13.28	9.39
DyCl ₃ .2(INH-PDAB)	20.01 (20.18)	13.79 13.91	13.01 13.22	10.57

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND RELATED BONDING PARAMETERS OF LANTHANIDE(III) CHLORIDE COMPLEXES OF INH-BENZ

Ln ³⁺	LnCl ₃ cm ⁻¹	Ln(INH-BENZ) ₂ Cl ₃ cm ⁻¹	J-level	(1-β)	β	b ^{1/2}	δ%	η
Pr	22 470	22 350	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂	0.005 34	0.994 66	0.036 55	0.536 86	0.002 68
	21 325	21 210	→ ³ P ₁	0.005 39	0.994 61	0.036 70	0.541 92	0.002 70
	20 750	20 600	→ ³ P ₀	0.007 22	0.992 78	0.042 48	0.727 25	0.003 63
	17 000	16 800	→ ¹ D ₂	0.011 76	0.988 24	0.054 22	1.189 99	0.005 93
Nd	19 550	19 450	⁴ I _{9/2} → ² G _{9/2}	0.005 11	0.994 09	0.035 74	0.513 62	0.002 56
			→ ⁴ G _{5/2} ,	0.006 33	0.993 67	0.039 78	0.637 03	0.003 19
			² G _{7/2} ,					
	13 660	13 620	→ ² S _{3/2} ,	0.002 92	0.997 08	0.027 01	0.292 85	0.001 47
			⁴ F _{7/2} ,					
		→ ⁴ F _{5/2}		0.005 61	0.994 39	0.037 44	0.564 16	
Sm	24 870	24 800	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ F _{9/2}	0.002 81	0.997 19	0.026 60	0.281 79	0.001 41
	24 000	23 800	→ ⁶ P _{5/2}	0.008 33	0.991 67	0.045 63	0.839 99	0.004 19
	21 550	21 500	→ ⁴ I _{13/2}	0.002 32	0.997 68	0.024 08	0.232 53	0.001 17

wavenumber at 1 560–1 550 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, indicating the involvement of N-atom of the azomethine group in coordination^{6,7}.

The strong bands observed at 1 575–1 520 and 1 080–1 000 cm⁻¹ are tentatively assigned^{7,8} to asymmetric and symmetric ν_{C=C} + ν_{C=N} of pyridine ring and pyridine ring breathings and deformations which remain practically unchanged in frequency and band intensities revealing non-involvement of pyridinic nitrogen in bonding to metal. However, the assignment⁹ is not unambiguous because N–N group of the ligand also absorbs in the region 1 000–900 cm⁻¹. The overall ir spectral evidence suggests that the ligands act as bidentate ligands coordinating through amide-oxygen and azomethine-nitrogen. The far-ir spectral bands in the ligands are practically unchanged in these complexes. But some new bands with medium to weak intensities appear at 440–360 cm⁻¹ in the complexes and are assigned to ν_{Ln-O} / ν_{Ln-N} modes². The ν_{M-Cl} is tentatively assigned at ~310 cm⁻¹ in these complexes.

Electronic spectra : Typical spectral data for solutions of Pr, Nd and Sm chloride complexes in CH₃CN is recorded in Table 2. The lanthanum(III) complexes have no significant absorption in the visible region. The bands observed in the Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} chelates may be due to transitions from the ground levels ³H₄, ⁴I_{9/2} and ⁶H_{5/2} to the excited J-levels of 4fⁿ configuration. The present data also indicate that the nephelauxatic values for different J-levels vary considerably; this is in agreement with the earlier findings².

We have also calculated various parameters (Table 2). The positive values for (1-β) and δ % in these complexes suggest that the bonding between the metal and the ligand is more covalent compared to the bonding between the metal and water^{10,11}. Comparatively smaller magnitude of b^{1/2} values also shows the involvement of the 4f-orbital in the metal-ligand bond to a very low degree¹¹.

Thermal studies : The thermograms of LnCl₃.2(INH-PDAB) are identical in their major details. The analyses of the thermolysis curves suggest that these complexes do not show the presence of water molecules either in or out of the coordination sphere. There is a change in the curves at 240–310° due to the loss of mass corresponding to one mole of INH-PDAB and at ~430° the remaining organic ligand is also lost. Finally at ~815°, stable lanthanide oxides are formed¹².

Experimental

The ligands INH-BENZ, INH-ANSL and INH-PDAB were synthesised as described earlier^{2,3}. The complexes were synthesised by the following a general method. The solutions of lanthanide chloride (1 mmol) and the corresponding ligand (2.1 mmol) in hot methanol (15 ml each) were mixed and refluxed on a water bath for ~2 h. On cooling in ice-bath, the resulting solid complex was separated out. It was repeatedly washed with diethyl ether and dried in a desiccator over P₄O₁₀.

All the physical measurements were performed by reported methods¹³.

References

1. H. K. DUGGAL and B. V. AGARWALA, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1992, 4, 1
2. R. K. AGARWAL and R. K. SARIN, *Polyhedron*, 1993, 12, 2411, R. K. AGARWAL, R. K. SARIN and R. PRASAD, *Polish J. Chem.*, 1993, 67, 1947.
3. R. K. AGARWAL, K. ARORA and P. DUTT, *Polyhedron*, 1994, 13, 957.
4. R. L. DUTTA and A. SYAMAL, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", Affiliated East-West Press, 1993; R. L. DUTTA and B. R. DAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, 22, 207.
5. L. J. BELLAMY, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1954.
6. P. K. RADHAKRISHNAN, P. INDRASENAN and C. G. R. NAIR, *Polyhedron*, 1984, 3, 67.
7. Y. KUMAR, P. D. SETHI and C. L. JAIN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, 67, 796.

NOTE

- 8 G R BURNS, *Inorg Chem*, 1968, **7**, 277, K SWAMINATHAN and N H IRVING, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1964, **26**, 1291
- 9 P S RADHAKRISHNAN and P INDRASENAN, *Indian J Chem, Sect A*, 1989, **28**, 234
- 10 C K JORGENSEN, *Proc Inorg Chem*, 1962, **4**, 73, S P SINHA, *Spectrochim Acta*, 1966, **22**, 57
- 11 J MOHAN, J P TANDON and N S GUPTA, *Inorg Chim Acta*, 1986, **111**, 187
- 12 G VICENTINI, K UMEDA and I GIOLITO, *An Acad Brasil Cienc*, 1977, **49**, 143
- 13 M C JAIN, R K SHARMA, A K SRIVASTAVA and P C JAIN, *J Inorg Nucl Chem*, 1979, **41**, 1305